

O‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ LATIFALARINING TARJIMASIDA EKVIVALENTLIK VA ADEKVATLIK MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada o‘zbek va ingliz tilidagi latifalarni tarjima qilish jarayonida duch kelinadigan ekvivalentlik va adekvatlik masalalari tahlil qilinadi. Latifalar – bu faqatgina kulgi manbai emas, balki murakkab lingvistik va madaniy birliklar bo‘lib, ularni tarjima qilish jarayoni nafaqat tilshunoslik, balki madaniyatshunoslik, psixologiya va semiotika nuqtayi nazaridan ham o‘ziga xos yondashuvni talab qiladi. Maqolada J.Ketford, G.Toury, A.D.Shveytsar, Mark Shattlworth va V.N.Komissarov singari yetakchi tarjima nazariyotchilarining fikrlari asosida ekvivalentlik darajalari va adekvatlik mezonlari muhokama qilinadi. Shuningdek, latifa tarjimasida yuzaga keladigan lingvistik va madaniy muammolar misollar bilan yoritiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: latifa tarjimasi, ekvivalentlik, adekvatlik, madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya, tarjima nazariyasi, funksional muvofiqlik, lingvistik moslik.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются проблемы эквивалентности и адекватности, возникающие в процессе перевода анекдотов с узбекского на английский язык и наоборот. Анекдоты представляют собой не только источник смеха, но и сложные лингвистические и культурные единицы, перевод которых требует особого подхода не только с точки зрения лингвистики, но также культурологии, психологии и семиотики. В статье обсуждаются уровни эквивалентности и критерии адекватности на основе взглядов ведущих теоретиков перевода, таких как Дж.Кэтфорд, Г.Тури, А.Д.Швейцер, Марк Шаттлворт и В.Н.Комиссаров. Также рассматриваются лингвистические и культурные трудности, возникающие при переводе анекдотов, с конкретными примерами.

Ключевые слова: перевод анекдотов, эквивалентность, адекватность, межкультурная коммуникация, теория перевода, функциональное соответствие, лингвистическое соответствие.

Abstract. This article analyzes the issues of equivalence and adequacy encountered in the process of translating jokes between Uzbek and English languages. Jokes are not only a source of laughter but also complex linguistic and cultural units, the translation of which requires a specific approach not only from a linguistic perspective but also from cultural studies, psychology, and semiotics. The article discusses the levels of equivalence and criteria of adequacy based on the views of leading translation theorists such as J.Catford, G.Toury, A.D.Schweitzer, Mark Shuttleworth, and V.N.Komissarov. Additionally, linguistic and cultural problems arising in joke translation are illustrated with examples.

Keywords: joke translation, equivalence, adequacy, intercultural communication, translation theory, functional correspondence, linguistic compatibility.

Introduction.

Jokes are a unique genre reflecting the culture and way of thinking of each nation, and the process of translating them manifests not only as language transfer but also as a complex form of intercultural interaction. The translation of English and Uzbek jokes often requires not only lexical correspondence but also cultural and functional compatibility. Therefore, this article analyzes the issues of equivalence and adequacy in joke translation, illuminating the role and problems of these two concepts in translation practice based on the views of prominent scholars. Furthermore, the influence of linguacultural and psycholinguistic factors on joke translation is analyzed through examples. Jokes are complex linguistic and psychological phenomena formed through the unique culture and language of each nation. Their translation is not merely changing the language but a distinctive process of conveying information and emotions from one culture to another. Issues of equivalence and adequacy hold a special place in the joke translation process, as they are necessary to ensure a complete and accurate translation of content. These issues require translation to be linguistically and culturally perfect, beyond merely translating words and phrases. Equivalence implies matching the meaning and structure of the target language to the original language. In this process, it is important to preserve the position and content of each element. The translation of English jokes into Uzbek often needs to maintain the same structure and meaning. For example, when translating "knock-knock jokes" into Uzbek, it is necessary to find a form suitable for the Uzbek language to preserve the original content. However, since each joke is connected to its culture, some changes may need to be introduced in the translation.

Equivalence and transposition relationships are one of the factors determining the importance of meaning. These relationships emphasize the relevance of certain pieces of knowledge by changing the form of expression. For example, focusing on the process of universalization, Kubryakova notes that its main function is to harmonize previous experience with new knowledge. According to her, conveying information in a concise form while making it understandable and clear is also important. Such linguistic units not only express meaning but also expand its expressive possibilities.[1] Equivalence is usually considered as the main feature and condition for the existence of translation, which, in turn, leads to the inclusion of the phenomenon of equivalence in the specific definition of translation itself. For example, English scholar J. Catford defines translation as replacing the textual material of one language with equivalent textual material in another language and emphasizes that the main task of translation theory is to determine the characteristics and conditions of translation equivalence.[2] It should be noted that the concept of "equivalence" has become a controversial issue among many linguists. The main reason for this is that the term denoting this concept is polysemous, and translation equivalence is interpreted differently. Some scholars compare translation equivalence with mathematical equivalence based on analogy, explaining the symmetrical and reversible nature of translation by this. For instance, J. Catford examines equivalence from a quantitative expression perspective. Understanding translation as replacing units of the source language with exact equivalents in the target language is expressed through the allegory of linguistic constraints, which later raised the issue of symmetry between languages and interpreted translation as a simple linguistic activity, without taking into account cultural, textual, and pragmatic factors.[3]

According to Toury, for a translation to be considered adequate, the translator must first remain faithful to the original text and not strive for full adaptation to the linguistic and literary norms of the target language. In other words, the translator should only make necessary changes so that the text in the target language retains the characteristics of the original to the maximum

extent. Such an approach can result in a translated text that does not conform to the literary and linguistic norms of the target language in some aspects.[4] The connection of discourse with ethnopsycholinguistic and linguacultural factors can be manifested in every aspect. This process can be observed from extralinguistic factors, especially from the proxemic aspects of communication, to communication strategies and tactics. It also affects from paralinguistic elements such as facial expressions and gestures to text structure and forms of expression. Additionally, it reflects from the spelling and syllabification of words to linguistic means considered "equivalent" in various languages. For example, the use of "thou" and "you" words in Russian, German, French, Spanish, and Swedish languages – in which situation, to whom, under what circumstances to address – is a constant problem for foreigners, and the wrong choice can lead to awkward situations or even offend the interlocutor.[5] According to Schweitzer, equivalence is considered the absolute criterion of translation, while adequacy is related to the translator's ability to adapt to the communicative situation. Adequate translation involves certain compromises, as the translator is sometimes forced to sacrifice some elements to preserve the main content of the text. Therefore, correct conveyance of important components takes precedence over complete correspondence in the translation process.[6] According to Mark Shuttleworth, a translated text can be considered adequate if it corresponds with the original text in at least one functional aspect. However, deviation from equivalence can only be justified in necessary cases; if it is based on the translator's personal decision, it is not acceptable. Complete equivalence implies that the translated text is as close as possible to the original and corresponds in communicative-functional aspects. Adequacy, on the other hand, is aimed at ensuring that the translation optimally meets the goals and objectives, in which process the content and functional characteristics of the text play an important role.[7]

In the translation process, the concepts of equivalence and adequacy are considered one of the main principles determining the quality of translation. These theoretical concepts are important not only from a linguistic perspective but also from cultural studies, psychology, and semiotics. This is because the translation process requires not only the substitution of linguistic units but also preserving the essence of the text in the context of a new culture. Komissarov, analyzing the levels of equivalence in translation, examines it at various levels, from direct semantic correspondence to contextual and pragmatic harmony. Such an approach shows that in the translation process, it is necessary to pay attention to the effectiveness and functional aspects of the text, not just limiting oneself to word-for-word correspondence.

Komissarov, in his work "Translation Theory (Linguistic Aspects)," proposed a theory of levels of equivalence, according to which correspondence relationships are formed between the original text and the translated text in the translation process. He distinguishes five levels in terms of content: the level of communicative purpose, the level of situation description, the level of sentence, the level of message, and the level of language signs.[8] According to Komissarov's theory, equivalence in translation consists of ensuring the maximum correspondence of content levels between the original and translated texts. Original and translated units may correspond at all levels or only at certain levels. There may be complete equivalents, partially corresponding equivalent units, or context-dependent equivalent statements in both languages. Their correct evaluation, selection, and application depend on the translator's skill, knowledge, creativity, and ability to take into account linguistic and extralinguistic factors. In the translation process, the translator must not only find and select an equivalent unit but also apply it correctly, creating communicatively appropriate statements in both languages. Komissarov distinguishes two types of equivalence. The first is potential equivalence, which means that texts in two languages have

maximum commonality in terms of content, and it can be called theoretical equivalence. The second is practical equivalence, which expresses the actual semantic proximity of the original and translated texts achieved by the translator during the translation process. The translator adapts the text to the original through various methods in the translation process, preserves the content as much as possible, and strives to achieve potential equivalence. Komissarov's classification is one of the approaches aimed at identifying types of equivalence.

Nida, who studied the issue of equivalence, divides it into dynamic and formal forms. Dynamic equivalence aims to preserve the general meaning and impact of the text, while formal equivalence strives to ensure grammatical and lexical correspondence. The theory of functional equivalence proposed by Nida differs from previous theories based on direct comparison of linguistic forms between the source language and the target language. Nida offers a new method of ensuring equivalence, recommending taking into account the receiver's attitude towards the text. According to him, the attitude of target language receivers towards the translated text should be as close as possible to the attitude of original text receivers towards the original text. Nida's theory of functional equivalence is based on three main aspects. First, the concept of equivalence. Functional equivalence can be defined as the closest natural equivalent of the source language message. Attention should be paid to three important terms in this definition: "closest," "natural," and "equivalent." Here, "equivalence" should be understood not in the sense of complete similarity, but from the point of view of "closeness." Functional equivalence translation is primarily focused on the equivalence of receivers' attitudes rather than linguistic forms. Using the concept of "equivalent," Nida emphasizes the need to ensure that the response of target language receivers is as close as possible to the response of source language receivers.[9] Dynamic equivalence is particularly important in the translation of jokes or humor, as the nature of this genre is closely related to cultural context. If the translator relies only on formal equivalence, the humorous effect of the joke may be lost.

Using the concept of "closest" in translation, Nida expresses the degree of closeness between the source language and the target language. Functional equivalence requires the highest degree of closeness. Here, the concept of "closest" is considered from two main aspects: the form of language and the meaning of expression. Ideally, the translated text should be as close as possible to the original text in both form and meaning. No aspect should be overemphasized at the expense of the other. However, a discrepancy between the language form and the meaning of expression inevitably arises in the translation process, especially when culturally loaded words and phrases are translated. The information being transmitted from the source language text directly determines how it is received by the target language receivers.[10] Therefore, in most cases, conveying the meaning and content of expression takes precedence over language forms to increase the level of equivalence. The translator's task is to bring the attitudes of representatives of different cultures towards the text as close as possible to each other.

The concept of adequacy implies the importance of conveying the text in a natural and understandable form, taking into account the purpose of the translation and the reader audience. Alekseeva explains adequate translation as a process carried out while preserving the communicative function of the original text. This means that the translator should pay attention to how words are perceived in the new cultural context rather than their direct correspondence. For example, in the translation of jokes, direct translation is sometimes illogical because the humorous aspect of the joke may depend on linguistic or cultural peculiarities.

Adequate translation should evoke the intellectual or emotional reaction intended by the author of the text in the listener or reader and implement the pragmatic purpose set by the

participants of the communication. The translation must fully comply with the goals of communication. From this perspective, the translator tries to recreate in the target language audience the effect that arose in the original text audience during the process of translating jokes. For this, they use various linguistic units and methods. The set of linguistic means aimed at producing the reaction intended by the author in the recipient of the translated text is called the pragmatic adaptation of the translation.[11] For many translators, the concept of "good," "quality," or "literary" translation is usually associated with the term "adequate translation." This concept is comprehensive, encompassing all the requirements for the quality of translation. By distinguishing three main aspects of these requirements, the following definition can be given to adequate translation. Adequate translation is a translation that achieves maximum equivalence to pragmatic goals during the translation process and does not contradict the norms of the target language. To elaborate on these requirements, we will analyze them in the context of typical translation errors. The first requirement is related to the equivalence of the translation. Adequate translation should convey the content or information in the original text (cognitive, expressive, and other information) as completely and accurately as possible, and also recreate the communicative effect planned by the author of the text in their message as in the original.[12]

In joke translation, linguistic and cultural differences are one of the main difficulties for the translator, as such texts may be based on metaphors, wordplay, irony, and paradoxes. For example, the English joke I told my suitcase there will be no vacation this year. Now I'm dealing with emotional baggage is based on wordplay, where the phrase "emotional baggage" can be understood in two different ways: on the one hand, it means emotional burden in a metaphorical sense, and on the other hand, the word "baggage" maintains the context of travel. Direct translation into Uzbek may result in the loss of the humorous effect of the joke. The translator can express it more freely while preserving the meaning as *Chamadonimga bu yil ta'til yo'qligini aytdim. Endi u bilan jiddiy muammolarim bor (I told my suitcase there will be no vacation this year. Now I have serious problems with it).*

In the process of joke translation, the translator is obliged to take into account the psychological and linguistic characteristics of their culture. Applying the principles of equivalence and adequacy in a balanced manner ensures that the translated joke is more understandable and sincere to a wider audience. In this case, the translator should not limit themselves to just the correct translation of words but try to preserve the spirit and content of the joke. At this point, the issues of equivalence and adequacy that arise in the process of joke translation serve as an important factor determining the quality of the translation. Ensuring harmony between these two concepts in translation develops intercultural understanding in addition to language change. Therefore, when translating jokes, it is important to pay attention to the meaning and structure of the original text, as well as to make necessary changes to convey the joke appropriately to the new culture. This approach helps to make jokes richer and more sincere.

Conclusion: Ensuring equivalence and adequacy in translating jokes depends not only on the translator's knowledge of the language but also on their intercultural competence. While equivalence ensures basic semantic correspondence in translation, adequacy emphasizes communicative and functional compatibility. As seen in the examples of English and Uzbek jokes, the translation of each joke should be carried out taking into account its cultural context. The levels of equivalence proposed by Komissarov, as well as the views on adequacy by Toury and Schweitzer, serve as an important theoretical basis for evaluating the quality of translation. Therefore, a balanced approach to both principles is necessary in the translation process, which

serves as the main factor in correctly conveying the original essence of the text in the target language.

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